

THE IMPORTANCE OF PROVIDING FACILITIES FOR FEMALE TRAVELERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15117397>

Annotation: In this article, statistics about women travelers in the tourism industry, creating facilities for female travelers in tourism destinations, female friendly hotels, giving special attention for women's choices, necessary services in creating luxury for women in hotels, taking into account safety system to provide a safe trip, recreational areas for women and importance of medical tourism for women and children are studied.

Keywords: female travelers, tourism services, security system, travel decision, tourism destinations, recreational tourism, medical tourism.

Today, the role of the tourism industry on the world scale is increasing sharply, which has an impact on the economic and social situation of the country. Each country develops and implements strategic programs in order to improve tourism infrastructure and create its tourist image. Because the development of the tourism industry affects the growth rates of the country's economy and gross domestic product. According to statistics, in 2023, the contribution of the tourism industry to the world gross domestic product was 11.5%, 9.9 trillion US dollars. In recent years, a number of reforms have been carried out to rapidly develop the tourism sector.

According to statistics, 64% of travelers around the world are women, and 36% are men. Women not only make up the majority of travelers, but also actively influence the choice of tourism destinations. According to research, 80% of travel decisions around the world are made by women. In addition, women account for 70% of travel spending worldwide. These numbers show us women's importance role in the growth of the tourism industry. Therefore, tourism industries should take into consideration creating facilities for women traveler in order to provide a satisfying travel experience.

First of all, accommodation facilities are important to increase women's self-confidence and to encourage them to travel more, and hotels in some countries and regions should establish their "Female friendly hotels" in accordance with international standards. It is necessary to create an image of

women-friendly hotels. In this case, the following types of services should be available in hotels to create comfort for female travelers.

Figure 1: Necessary services in creating luxury for women in hotels¹

First of all, security in hotels is important for women travelers. In this case, it is necessary to install surveillance cameras in hotels, to have enough security guards, and to install lighting systems at night. Female guests are served by female staff, which makes it more convenient for travelers. Also, the availability of taxi services in hotels for female travelers provides another comfort and safety. Because there may be difficulties in going to and from the hotel to tourist attractions.

Another aspect that women always pay attention to is cleanliness and hygiene products of high quality. Chaos can have a bad effect on the minds of travelers. Hygiene and cleanliness are important criteria for hotels to ensure guest satisfaction and create a positive brand image. The better the hygienic conditions in the hotel, the more it serves as an incentive for tourists to return.

In our opinion, the establishment of a separate women's hotels will ensure a high level of comfort in services for female travelers. Nowadays, "Women Only Hotels" are developing all over the world. For example, the hotels "Arya Wellness" located in Indonesia and "9h nine hours' woman" in Japan offer a number of services to their customers. For example, at the 9h nine hours' woman hotel, women can get healthy sleep patterns, stress management techniques and yoga classes. In addition, women-only events in such hotels provide comfort for women.

Also, existing hotels should have separate floors for women or separate rooms for them. According to information, many female tourists prefer to have rooms near the elevator for safety reasons. Also, the rooms for women should have a special design, that is, in light colors, with curtains, and of course, there should be necessary equipment for women, such as iron and hair dryers. Creating childcare rooms for family tourists, i.e., swings and other facilities for babies and children, ensures the development of hotel services.

Being helpful and showing respect for guests are important elements in the hotel industry, and employees should be trained to deal with women and young children. Rude behavior not only affects the reputation of the hotel, but also affects the impressions of female travelers.

Another convenience is that the hotel will have activities designed for female guests, including a separate swimming pool, fitness club, sports training, and beauty salon services, which will also provide convenience for Muslim female tourists. These include health centers and special Spa services for women.

According to UNWTO World Tourism Organization experts, tourists travel primarily to see and learn about a new culture, and the second important motive is health and rest, aimed at restoring both mental and physiological conditions. In the period of globalization, the increase in the tourism goals of tourists in the tourism industry prompted the emergence of many types of tourism in the industry. Recreational tourism has become popular in recent years due to the following factors:

- Covid-19 pandemic;
- Environmental pollution;
- Economic and social instability;
- Natural disasters;
- Intensification of industrial facilities.

It is known that the Covid-19 pandemic did not fail to affect the whole world. In particular, sharp declines were observed in the tourism industry, which had a significant impact on the flow of tourists. However, we can observe an increase in the demand for health centers in the years after the pandemic. Also, while technological developments have created a number of conveniences, they have also caused negative consequences, i.e. deterioration of the ecological situation. This, in turn, has led to an increase in the number of vacationers in clean, green areas and coastal areas. In addition, political instability in many countries (Russia-Ukraine, Iraq-Palestine), natural disasters (earthquake in

Turkey, flood in Kazakhstan) gave impetus to the development of recreational tourism. The above factors caused the demand for recreational areas as a touristic destination.

The results of our research show that providing special services for women, using the potential of recreational areas, will contribute to the development of health centers. In addition, the establishment of separate floors and rooms for women or mother-child rooms for women with young children in sanatorium-resort centers, as well as the introduction of special discounts to encourage their arrival, will not fail to be effective. In addition, the organization of various concerts and shows in sanatorium spa centers allows women to have cultural recreation while increasing travel impressions. Another important facility in the centers is the presence of various sports activities and Spa services for women and young children.

In addition to recreational tourism destinations, another purpose of tourism for women is medicine, which can include various cosmetic surgeries, eco or maternity purposes, and various examinations. According to statistics, Turkey is one of the first in Europe and Asia in terms of medical tourism. In 2023, 2 million patients from different countries came to Turkey and paid a total of 20 billion US dollars. Patients prefer to go to Turkey for treatment due to the following reasons:

- World-class quality services;
- Cheap prices;
- Number of accredited healthcare facilities;
- Fast service;
- Infrastructure;
- Hospitality;
- Rich cultural heritage and unique landscapes.

Conclusion:

To conclude, increasing the flow of tourists, attracting mainly female travelers, with the rational use of tourism resources will contribute to the socio-economic development of the region. Female travelers definitely bring their colleagues or family members with them, or at least recommend tourism services to others through social networks. This in turn, ensures industrial development. Also, female travelers are important in the tourism industry due to their long stay and high spending. The results of our research show that the development of tourism services for female travelers such as female friendly hotels, recreational areas, medical tourism will bring the flow of female tourists.

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